

Comparison of Patient Reported Preferences for Digital and Alginate Impression Techniques

1. Dr. Bhagyashree Desai*,** (Ph.D. Scholar)
2. Dr. Aakash B. Shah** (Ph.D. Guide, Head and Professor)

* Corresponding Author

**Department of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics, Faculty of Dental Science, Dharmsinh Desai University, Nadiad, Gujarat, India.

ABSTRACT:

Background: In this era of technological evolution, numerous innovations like intraoral scanners have been introduced and have changed the way of modern orthodontic practice. In patient care, it is of prime importance to understand the patient's perception, acceptance, and experiences regarding an invention. As their appraisal may or may not always be positive depending on various demographics and ethnicity. So, this study was carried out with the objectives to compare comfort experienced and reported by patients between traditional alginate and digital impression techniques as well as to generate evidence regarding patients' perceptions & preferences in particular Indian Orthodontic patient population.

Materials and method: A prospective comparative study was conducted including 138 patients reporting to department for Orthodontic treatment. Impressions were made using both the techniques; i.e. traditional (alginate) as well as digital intraoral scanning methods. TRIOS Color intraoral scan and Tropicalgin™ were used for digital and conventional impressions respectively. Patients were then randomly assigned using computer generated sequences for acquiring impressions by both techniques followed by recording their preferences. The data analysis was performed using SPSS software at significance level of $p \leq 0.05$.

Results: The response rate for the study was quite high (93.37%). Data indicated overall preference for **digital impression** in the domain of overall comfort level experienced and reported by majority of patients (71.3%) during impression making procedure which was statistically significant. ($p < 0.001$)

Conclusion: Digital impressions made with Intraoral scanners appear to be an acceptable as well as suitable alternative to conventional impression in orthodontic practice from the perspective of patients' comfort, experience and preferences for a particular Indian orthodontic patient population of a developing region.

Keywords: *Patient reported Preferences, Orthodontic patients, Digital impression, Alginate Impression.*

INTRODUCTION:

With the 3D systems coming into light along with the introduction of digital impressions and scanning systems in the field of dentistry in mid 1980s, the gain in their popularity, demand and acceptance within a decade was predicted.^{1,2} Recent technological advances have made intraoral scans and digital models a possibility and a promising alternative to conventional alginate impressions. With evidence supporting the accuracy of digital impression techniques, their adaptation in orthodontic practices is increasing.^{3,4}

Intraoral scanners are adjudged increasingly useful in routine orthodontic practice. Virtual models offer patients a three-dimensional (3D) image simulating the work needed to be done, its progress, and expected result. Through this procedure, the patient and the orthodontist achieve a more direct communication, with the former having feeling of active participation in treatment.⁵⁻⁸ Recently; customised, 3D printed appliances & clear aligners are being extensively as well as efficiently used for orthodontic treatment. In most cases that demands for scanners to be used.⁹

Though the technical aspects like accuracy, performance, accessibility, compatibility and user-friendliness have been evaluated thoroughly, patient-reported information including experiences, preferences, comfort and satisfaction are yet to be investigated extensively. Previous studies reporting patient perceptions have been carried out in various developed parts of the globe where intraoral scanners and digital impressions might not be

one of the most recent and novel advancements. However, especially in populations of a developing parts of Country and world overall evidence still lacks.^{10,11} It is suggested that subjects' demographics may have impact on the expectations of the patients.^{4,10,11,12}

On top of RCTs, it is salient part of evidence to have Patient reported outcomes, simultaneously focused on technical aspects and clinicians' Point of views.¹⁻⁴ Additionally, incorporating innovations in academic set ups, might bring us a step closer towards a futuristic set up aiming at replacing alginate impression with digital.¹³ Moreover, commencement of studies involving larger sample sizes are also required, suggested and recommended by previous researches as future scopes.^{4,11,14} Hence, to look after these needs towards appraising novel findings, compare them with existing data and to enhance current evidence base while filling in the voids of existing literature this study regarding patient reported preferences was planned and conducted.¹⁵

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This prospective comparative survey study was carried out in the Department of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics, Faculty of Dental Science, from an academic set-up of DD University after getting approval from the institutional ethical committee. A total of 138 participants were initially included and enrolled in the study fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria, having age in the range of 14 to 23 years. [The sample size calculation was done with power analysis having 0.05% alpha error, 95% power of the study.]

Methodology: The study design was inspired by previous studies,^{2,4,16} and digital scans and conventional impressions were acquired in random sequence from the same patients. Randomization was generated with the Excel program and allocation was hidden in consecutively numbered, closed envelopes. According to this, half of the patients first had conventional impressions and the other half had digital scans.²⁴ All the patients got impressions taken with Conventional method utilising Alginate with Zhermack Tropicalgin™, and Digital impression/scan acquired by the TRIOS Color (3Shape, Copenhagen, Denmark™). Immediately after the acquisition of both the impressions (on the same day), each participant was asked to report their preference denoting the comfort level experienced during the impression making procedure prior to end of the appointment. Each patient would have 3 options to choose from: (i) Conventional- Alginate Impression, (ii) Digital impression (Scanning procedure) (iii) No Preference. Towards developing a novel survey instrument, this survey was conducted and the patients filled out forms reporting experiences and preferences regarding other aspects as well.

Single principal investigator conducted the survey, by interviewing patients *Face-to-face*.

The statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 25.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages were computed to summarize the demographic variables and patient-reported preferences. The Chi-square test was applied to examine associations between categorical variables such as participants' preference or experience with impression techniques.

RESULTS:

The study showed high response rate of 129/138=93.47%. Out of 138 participants enrolled initially, 9 eventually were not able to participate out of either unwillingness or due to other feasibility reasons towards study design.

Out of 129 respondents, n=59(45.73%) were males, whereas, 71(55.03%) were females. **(Graph 1)**

Graph 1: Distribution of study participants according to Gender.

The results of the present study showed clear preference of the maximum number of participants, i.e. Out of total n=129, 92(71.30%) opting for “Digital Impression”, when asked about comfort level experienced during the impression taking procedure, followed by n=27(20.90%) choosing conventional “Alginate Impression” technique. The least number n=10(7.8%) of participants chose “No preference” option. All these findings were statistically significant. (P<0.001) [Table 1; Figure 1]

Table 1: Comparison of Participants’ Preferences for different perceptions about Alginate and Digital Impression techniques reported through responses

<u>Participants’ perception</u>	<u>Alginate Impression</u>	<u>Digital Impression</u>	<u>No Preference</u>	<u>Total</u>	<u>P value</u>
	<u>n(%)</u>	<u>n(%)</u>	<u>n(%)</u>	<u>N(%)</u>	
Comfort Level	27(20.90)	92(71.30)	10(7.80)	129(100.00)	<0.001**

***Statistically significant $p \leq 0.05$, Chi-square test.*

Figure 1: Comparison of Patients’ preference between Alginate and Digital Impression techniques.

DISCUSSION:

Intraoral scanners have mostly been investigated regarding their accuracy, reliability, and precision.¹⁷ Patients' perceptions towards the procedure have been mainly examined in the areas of prosthodontics and implantology, but Patient reported outcomes (PROs) following full arch impression taking that could be more relevant to the field of orthodontics have yet to be extensively examined especially in orthodontic patients of developing Indian population.¹⁰

The study population was standardized and homogenized by including subjects with no previous experience with conventional or digital impressions in their dental history. To investigate the clinical outcomes of the two impression techniques, homogenizing the study population is an acceptable clinical research practice to minimize chances of bias. This step is essential for avoiding bias reported of patients with prior experience with the dental impression procedure/s.²

Undertaking face to face interview has merits including *High response rates, clarifications and better understanding of questions if necessary*; control over respondent selection, and ease to motivate respondents.¹⁸

The results of present study reported significantly higher and majority (71.3%) of participants opting for "Digital Impressions" as preferred method from comfort point of view, followed by 20.9% choosing "Alginate Impression" option as preferred technique and the least number of participants (7.8%) selected "No preference" option. Overall, the fact that participants may prefer scan over a conventional impression comes as no surprise.¹⁰

Similar results were depicted by previous studies existing in the literature. In general, that most of patients preferred the digital methods.^{2,14,19,20} However, in contrast with our findings, Grunheid et al.²¹, reported that participants preferred the alginate impressions over IOS. Also, Conversely, the study of Burzynski et al.³ suggests that participants who experienced conventional (alginate) methods showed less preference towards digital methods.

Limitations of our study and future scopes:

- Only one type of conventional impression, i.e., -alginate and only 1 scanner brand for digital impression were used and assessed. We could have compared other conventional impression materials and scanners. This was an initial survey conducted towards developing a novel Survey instrument, similar studies as well as in depth studies can be commenced in various patient populations across different parts of the country having different demographic- [social & economical] and ethnic backgrounds.

CONCLUSION:

Within the scopes of this study, it could be concluded that Digital impression technique was preferred by maximum number=92(71.3%) of participants from the point of **comfort level experienced** during impression making procedure. Digital impressions made with Intraoral scanners seem to be an acceptable as well as suitable alternative to conventional impression in orthodontic practice from the perspective of patients' comfort, experience and preferences for a particular Indian orthodontic patient population of a developing region. The study done in this part of India, with high number of participants and higher response rate could benefit the fraternity towards better patient experience along with farther expanding the pool of evidence base.

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